

Fundamental Limits of Decentralized Self-Regulating Random Walks

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Abstract—Self-regulating random walks (SRRWs) are decentralized token-passing processes on a graph allowing nodes to locally *fork*, *terminate*, or *pass* tokens based only on a return-time age statistic. We study SRRWs on a finite connected graph under a lazy reversible walk, with exogenous *trap* deletions summarized by the absorption pressure $\Lambda_{\text{del}} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}} \zeta(u)\pi(u)$ and a global per-visit fork cap q . Using exponential envelopes for return-time tails, we build graph-dependent Laplace envelopes that universally bound the stationary fork intensity of any age-based policy, leading to an effective triggering age A_{eff} . A mixing-based block drift analysis then yields controller-agnostic stability limits: any policy that avoids extinction and explosion must satisfy a *viability inequality* (births can overcome Λ_{del} at low population) and a *safety inequality* (trap deletions plus deliberate terminations dominate births at high population). Under corridor-wise versions of these conditions, we obtain positive recurrence of the population to a finite corridor.

Index Terms—Decentralized Systems, random walks, token passing, fault tolerance, Markov chains.

I. INTRODUCTION

Decentralized algorithms enable processing and learning over large-scale networks without relying on an omniscient central coordinator. In many applications, information is propagated by *tokens* that move across the network according to a random walk (RW) on a communication graph. This leads to communication-efficient protocols in which only a few nodes are active at each time instance. Examples include RW-based decentralized learning/optimization and message passing; see, e.g., [1]–[5].

A central challenge is *failure resilience*. If a token is lost due to a node or link failure, then the corresponding RW trajectory (and the carried computation) is disrupted. Recent work has proposed *self-regulating random walks* (SRRWs) and closely related *self-duplicating* mechanisms as lightweight, fully decentralized approaches to mitigate such losses and improve robustness of RW-based learning (e.g., [6], [7]): upon each token arrival, a node uses only locally available information—typically the time since its last token visit (a local “age” or return-time statistic)—to decide whether to (i) pass the token, (ii) fork (duplicate) it into additional copies, or (iii) deliberately terminate it to curb overload. Empirically

and algorithmically, carefully designed SRRW controllers can maintain a desired token population and react to failures without a central monitor.

At the same time, recent studies have highlighted fundamental vulnerabilities of RW-based decentralized learning under localized adversarial disruptions, including Pac-Man-style attacks [8]. These observations further motivate a principled understanding of what behaviors are intrinsically attainable in SRRW systems on a given graph.

Despite this progress, a basic question remains open: *What are the intrinsic limits of SRRWs, independent of the controller?* Here, a *controller* refers to the decentralized control logic implemented at each node, which prescribes based only on local age information (and possibly a coarse population estimate), whether to fork, terminate, or pass a newly arrived token. In practice, controllers are typically tuned by empirically validating the performance of chosen local thresholds and probabilities. It is not clear how to choose those thresholds based on the network properties, nor which behaviors are fundamentally attainable on a given network, and which are ruled out by the geometry and mixing properties of the underlying RW.

This paper takes a controller-agnostic viewpoint and focuses on the most basic stability requirements for SRRW populations: *viability* (avoiding extinction) and *safety* (avoiding explosion). We consider a finite, connected graph supporting multiple tokens evolving as lazy RWs with a stationary distribution π . A subset of nodes forms a *trap set* $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}$: when a token visits $u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}$, it is deleted with probability $\zeta(u) \in [0, 1]$, inducing an intrinsic *absorption pressure* $\Lambda_{\text{del}} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}} \zeta(u)\pi(u)$. At non-trap nodes, the controller may fork or deliberately terminate tokens, subject to a per-visit fork cap $q \in (0, 1]$ and a one-action-per-visit rule.

Our main technical tool is a pair of graph-dependent *Laplace envelopes* built from return-time tails of the underlying lazy reversible walk. These envelopes universally bound the stationary fork intensity achievable by *any* age-based policy, and lead to a single scalar summary of the controller via an *effective triggering age* A_{eff} , capturing the typical age scale at which the policy acts in a steady state.

Main result and contributions. We show that any decentralized age-based policy that avoids extinction and explosion

must satisfy two universal inequalities: (i) a *viability* condition requiring that the achievable fork intensity can overcome the absorption pressure when the population is small; and (ii) a *safety* condition requiring that trap deletions plus deliberate terminations dominate births when the population is large. The proof of our main result is based on the following components:

- (I) *Controller-agnostic fork envelopes* that bound the stationary per-visit fork probability of any age-based policy via two graph-dependent Laplace envelopes.
- (II) The *effective triggering age* A_{eff} as a single scalar summary of a possibly non-uniform decentralized policy through envelope matching.
- (III) The resulting *universal viability/safety limits* and a *corridor recurrence* guarantee (Theorem 1).

These statements are expressed entirely via Λ_{del} , the fork cap q , the Laplace envelopes evaluated at A_{eff} , and the mean intentional termination rate. Moreover, under corridor-wise versions of the inequalities, the population is positive recurrent to a finite corridor.

Relation to prior failure models. Our trap-set formulation subsumes common SRRW settings studied in the literature: The *probabilistic, location-independent failures* [6] correspond to taking $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}} = \mathcal{V}$ with suitable deletion probabilities $\zeta(u)$ (possibly uniform), so that every node can delete a token exogenously. The *localized adversarial deletion* (“Pac-Man”) model [8], where a single malicious node deletes all visiting tokens, corresponds to taking $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}} = \{u^*\}$ and $\zeta(u^*) = 1$. In both cases, Theorem 1 yields graph-dependent constraints that any decentralized age-based controller must obey, and provides theoretical insights for tuning the parameters of the algorithms in [6]–[8].

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Notation and Model

Notation. We start with the common notation used throughout the paper. Lower case and upper case bold letters denote vectors and matrices, respectively, e.g., \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{X} . The entries of a vector \mathbf{x} of length n are denoted by x_1, \dots, x_n . The identity matrix is denoted by \mathbf{I} . Sets are denoted by calligraphic letters, e.g., \mathcal{V} , and $|\cdot|$ denotes their cardinality, e.g., $|\mathcal{V}|$. For a positive integer n , we let Δ^{n-1} be the probability simplex over \mathbb{R}^n , i.e., $\Delta^{n-1} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n : x_i \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, n, \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 1\}$. For $a, b \in \mathbb{R}, b > a$, we define $[a, b] := \{x : x \in \mathbb{R}, a \leq x \leq b\}$, $(a, b] := \{x : x \in \mathbb{R}, a < x \leq b\}$ and $(a, b) := \{x : x \in \mathbb{R}, a < x < b\}$.

System model. Consider a finite connected undirected graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ with n nodes, where \mathcal{V} represents the set of nodes and \mathcal{E} the set of edges. For nodes $u, v \in \mathcal{V}$, u and v are said to be neighbors if the edges (u, v) and (v, u) are in \mathcal{E} . The nodes want to collaborate to achieve a desired task, e.g., propagating information through the graph or running a decentralized machine learning algorithm.

We focus on a setting in which not all nodes can be active at the same time. To that end, we consider a collection of $Z_0 \ll n$ tokens distributed to Z_0 nodes. Each node holding a token

is active and may run any necessary task (e.g., computation, measurement, sensing . . .) and sends the token to one of its neighbors, chosen according to a transition matrix \mathbf{P} , i.e., for $u, v \in \mathcal{V}$, $P_{u,v}$ is the probability of node u sending the token to node v . This process continues, with token communication occurring at discrete time steps t . Therefore, the tokens move through the graph as independent RWs.

B. Problem Formulation

Traps and actions. The problem we study is that of token (or RW) failure throughout the process. We model the failures by an arbitrary set $\mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ of unreliable nodes. When a token is visiting a node $v \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}$, with probability $\zeta(v) \in [0, 1]$, the node will not propagate the token further, thus permanently deleting the corresponding RW. With no action taken to recover from failures, all RWs will eventually be deleted. To recover from RW deletion, we consider a decentralized policy that allows nodes to take actions based on their local observations.

When a node u is visited by a token, it will run any necessary task and take one of the following actions: (i) *fork* the RW by creating a duplicate copy of the RW corresponding to the visiting token and propagating the RWs to two different neighbors; (ii) *terminate* the RW by not propagating the token any further; or (iii) *pass* the token to a neighbor. We denote by $a_u(t) \in \{\text{fork}, \text{terminate}, \text{pass}\}$ the action taken by node u at time t . We restrict our attention to age-based actions. Each node u maintains a *return-time age* of the tokens defined as $A_u(t) := t - L_u(t)$, where $L_u(t)$ is the last time step at which u was visited by a token. The action taken by node u will be based on $A_u(t)$.

Weak average crossing (W-AC) rule. We consider a local randomized policy μ_u and fix a per-node soft age triggers $A_u^l \geq 0$ and $0 \leq A_u^s \leq A_u^l$. A node u visited by a token at time t compares $A_u(t)$ to A_u^s and A_u^l . If $A_u(t) \in (A_u^s, A_u^l)$, the node passes the token, i.e., $a_u(t) := \mu_u(A_u(t)) = \text{pass}$. Otherwise, if $A_u(t) \geq A_u^l$, with pre-determined probability $q_u^{\text{fork}} \in (0, 1]$, node u forks the visiting RW. Thus, A_u^l dictates *when* a fork is permitted and q_u^{fork} dictates *how strongly* each visit may lead to a fork. If, however, $A_u(t) \leq A_u^s$, with pre-determined probability $q_u^{\text{term}} \in (0, 1]$, node u deliberately terminates the visiting RW. In this paper, we focus on analyzing the choice of q_u^{fork} and A_u^l and assume $A_u^l = A$ for all $u \in \mathcal{V}$. Instead of additionally analyzing the choice of A_u^s and q_u^{term} , we abstract them away and consider an average global intentional termination rate K_{term} . A detailed analysis of A_u^s and q_u^{term} will be provided in future work.

Population dynamics and controller. Let Z_t denote the number of RWs alive at time step t , i.e., the number of tokens sent at time step $t - 1$. The goal is to design a decentralized controller, i.e., suitable values of q_u^{fork} and A , such that we can guarantee with high probability that Z_t remains within a *corridor* $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$ for desired constants $0 < Z_{\text{low}} < Z_{\text{high}} < \infty$. We say a policy *avoids extinction* if $\Pr(\exists t : Z_t \leq 0) = 0$, and *avoids explosion* if $\Pr(\sup_{t \geq 0} Z_t = \infty) = 0$. (Equivalently, Z_t remains in \mathbb{N} without hitting 0 or diverging.)

We consider a lazy transition matrix $\mathbf{P} := (\epsilon \mathbf{I} + (1 - \epsilon) \mathbf{P}')$, where $\epsilon > 0$ and \mathbf{P}' is a simple transition matrix satisfying $P'_{u,u} = 0$, $u \in \mathcal{V}$. Hence, a stationary distribution $\boldsymbol{\pi} \in \Delta^{n-1}$ satisfying $\boldsymbol{\pi}^\top = \boldsymbol{\pi}^\top \mathbf{P}'$ exists and is reached after the RWs have circulated the graph for longer than $T_{\text{mix}} = \mathcal{O}(\lambda_2 \log n)$, where λ_2 the spectral gap¹ of \mathbf{P}' .

Therefore, in our analyses that operate on time scales, we will assume $t \geq T_{\text{mix}}$ so that we can treat the token locations on the graph as approximately independent draws from the stationary law $\boldsymbol{\pi}$. In this regime, the model for idealized expected per-time-step deletion rate induced purely by the graph topology and the trap profile $\zeta(\cdot)$ is $\Lambda_{\text{del}} := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}} \zeta(u) \boldsymbol{\pi}(u)$, which we term the *absorption pressure*.

Effective triggering age A_{eff} . A key difficulty is that a general decentralized age-based controller may be *non-uniform* across nodes and may randomize its decisions, so its steady-state *global* fork intensity cannot be summarized by a single explicit threshold parameter. To obtain a controller-agnostic description, we compress the steady-state behavior of any W-AC policy into a single scalar, called the *effective triggering age* A_{eff} . Concretely, let p_{fork} denote the long-run per-visit fork probability induced by the controller after mixing. Using return-time tail bounds, we define two graph-dependent *Laplace envelopes* $L_\pi^+(\cdot)$ and $L_\pi^-(\cdot)$ such that for every $A \geq 0$ a uniform W-AC policy with trigger A would satisfy $q L_\pi^+(A) \leq p'_{\text{fork}}(A) \leq q L_\pi^-(A)$. For a general (possibly non-uniform) policy, we then define A_{eff} as any value satisfying the envelope-matching condition

$$q L_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \leq p_{\text{fork}} \leq q L_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}),$$

so that A_{eff} serves as a single age scale summarizing the controller at the drift level. When the policy is uniform with $A_u^l = A$ and a common fork cap $q_u^{\text{fork}} = q$, we have $A_{\text{eff}} = A$.

III. MAIN RESULT

For the setting described above, we derive a principled method for choosing values $A = A_u$ and $q = q_u^{\text{fork}}$ that guarantee Z_t remains in the desired corridor with high probability. We define the *mean intentional termination rate* as $K_{\text{term}} := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \boldsymbol{\pi}(u) q_u^{\text{term}}(A_u(t))$, where the expectation is taken over the stationary distribution of ages A_u induced by the policy. Thus, K_{term} represents the average probability that a single RW visit results in an intentional termination.

We now turn to controller-agnostic stability limits for the SRRW population. Our goal is *not* to optimize a particular

¹The spectral gap of a reversible Markov chain with transition matrix \mathbf{P}' is defined as $\lambda_2 = 1 - \rho_2$, where ρ_2 is the second-largest eigenvalue (in magnitude) of \mathbf{P}' . It quantifies the rate at which the random walk mixes toward its stationary distribution: a larger λ_2 implies faster convergence and a smaller mixing time. The mixing time satisfies the standard spectral bound

$$T_{\text{mix}}(\epsilon) \leq \frac{1}{1 - \lambda_2} \log\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon \boldsymbol{\pi}_{\min}}\right),$$

where $\lambda_2 < 1$ is the second largest eigenvalue of the lazy transition matrix and $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\min} = \min_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \boldsymbol{\pi}(u)$. For roughly uniform stationary laws ($\boldsymbol{\pi}_{\min} \asymp 1/n$), this scales as $\mathcal{O}(\lambda_2^{-1} \log n)$ [5, Ch. 12].

controller, but to identify graph-dependent constraints that *any* decentralized age-based (W-AC) policy must satisfy in order to keep the population viable (avoid extinction) and safe (avoid explosion). Concretely, we characterize the admissible steady-state fork intensity via Laplace-envelope bounds and translate these bounds into universal *viability* and *safety* inequalities. Under corridor-wise margins, these conditions further imply positive recurrence of $\{Z_t\}$ to a finite corridor.

Theorem 1. For any decentralized age-based policy obeying the W-AC rule that avoids extinction and explosion, the following conditions must hold:

$$\text{(V)} \quad q L_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{(S)} \quad q L_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} \leq 0, \quad (2)$$

where A_{eff} is the effective triggering age, K_{term} is the mean intentional termination rate, and $q \in (0, 1]$ denotes the *global per-visit fork bound*, i.e.

$$q := \sup_{u \in \mathcal{V}} q_u^{\text{fork}}, \quad \text{and} \quad q_u^{\text{fork}} \leq q \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{V} \geq 0.$$

Here, $q_u^{\text{fork}}(A)$ is the probability that node u forks a visiting token when its return-time age exceeds A . Conversely, suppose there exist constants $0 < Z_{\text{low}} < Z_{\text{high}} < \infty$ such that:

- the **viability condition (V)** holds whenever the population is below the corridor, which guarantees a strictly positive net birth rate when the system is under-populated;
- the **safety condition (S)** holds whenever the population exceeds the corridor, which guarantees a strictly negative net drift (births are dominated by trap-deletions plus deliberate terminations) when the population is too large.

Then the population process $\{Z_t\}$ is *positive recurrent to the corridor* $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$. That is, the Markov chain returns to the interval $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$ infinitely often with finite mean return time, and it spends a nonzero fraction of time inside the corridor in the steady state. Equivalently, $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$ is a positive recurrent (petite) set² for the chain.

To prove Theorem 1, we first analyze the token distribution on the graph and then analyze the resulting global fork intensity p_{fork} based on the token distribution and the choice of q_u^{fork} . Bounding p_{fork} using Lagrange envelopes then provides us with the value of A_{eff} . With this information at hand, we provide a sketch of the proof of Theorem 1 and defer the formal proof to [10, Section B].

IV. TOKEN DISTRIBUTION ON THE GRAPH

Our goal is to derive *controller-agnostic* necessary conditions for *viability* (avoiding extinction) and *safety* (avoiding explosion), in terms of graph-dependent quantities and the steady-state fork intensity induced by the policy.

²A subset C of the state space is called a *petite set* if there exists a nontrivial measure ν and an integer-valued sampling distribution $a(\cdot)$ such that for all $x \in C$ and all measurable A , $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a(n) P^n(x, A) \geq \nu(A)$. Intuitively, petite sets are those from which the chain can reach all regions of the state space with uniformly positive probability under a randomized (multi-step) transition. Petite sets generalize the notion of “small sets” and are the key objects used in the Foster–Lyapunov criteria for positive recurrence [9].

At discrete time t , the network hosts Z_t live lazy RWs, each evolving independently according to \mathbf{P} . Since each live token makes exactly one node visit per time step, “*per-visit*” and “*per-token per-step*” are interchangeable. Hence, any global expected count over one step scales linearly with Z_t .

Before analyzing the control and stability properties of the token population, we first establish how tokens are distributed across nodes in the absence of control. This baseline spatial distribution determines the expected rates at which tokens visit or disappear at each node. Lemma 1 formalizes this equilibrium distribution and its convergence properties.

Lemma 1 (Stationary distribution of an undirected RW). Let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ be a finite, connected, undirected graph and let $\deg(u)$ denote the number of edges of node $u \in \mathcal{V}$, i.e., $\deg(u) := |\{(u, v) : v \in \mathcal{V}, (u, v) \in \mathcal{E}\}|$. Consider either:

- (i) **Simple (non-lazy) random walk (SRW)**: $P'_{uv} = 1/\deg(u)$ if $(u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$, and 0 otherwise; or
- (ii) **Weighted (non-lazy) random walk (reversible RW)**: edges have symmetric weights $w_{uv} = w_{vu} \geq 0$, and

$$P'_{uv} = \frac{w_{uv}}{w_u}, \quad w_u := \sum_{v:(u,v) \in \mathcal{E}} w_{uv}.$$

Define

$$\pi(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{\deg(u)}{2|\mathcal{E}|}, & \text{for (i),} \\ \frac{w_u}{\sum_{x \in \mathcal{V}} w_x}, & \text{for (ii).} \end{cases}$$

Then, π is a stationary distribution: $\pi^\top \mathbf{P}' = \pi^\top$ and $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) = 1$. The chain is irreducible (every node is reachable from every other node). If, in addition, it is made *lazy* via $\mathbf{P} = (\epsilon \mathbf{I} + (1 - \epsilon) \mathbf{P}')$, $\epsilon > 0$, it becomes aperiodic while preserving the same stationary distribution. Consequently, for any initial distribution α ,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \alpha^\top (\mathbf{P})^t = \pi^\top.$$

Moreover, if Z_t independent tokens evolve according to \mathbf{P} in stationarity, the random vector of node occupancies follows Multinomial(Z_t, π).³

The proof of Lemma 1 consists of few mathematical operations and is given in [10, Section A]. The stationary distribution π plays a central role in connecting the structure of the network to the large-scale behavior of the tokens. It describes how often, in the long run, a typical RW visits each part of the graph. This long-run visiting pattern determines how frequently nodes initiate forks or terminations, how often tokens encounter trap nodes, and how much overall termination pressure the adversarial regions of the graph exert

³The notation Multinomial(Z_t, π) denotes the multinomial distribution over the n nodes, parameterized by the total number of tokens Z_t and probability vector $\pi = (\pi(u))_{u \in \mathcal{V}}$. If $N_u(t)$ is the number of tokens located at node u at time t , then $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} N_u(t) = Z_t$ and $\Pr\{N_1 = k_1, \dots, N_n = k_n\} = \frac{Z_t!}{\prod_{u \in \mathcal{V}} k_u!} \prod_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u)^{k_u}$ for $k_u \geq 0$ and $\sum_u k_u = Z_t$. Each marginal satisfies $\mathbb{E}[N_u(t)] = Z_t \pi(u)$, giving the expected number of tokens at node u under stationarity.

on the system. All later discussions of viability, safety, and operational cost rely on this stationary picture, because it allows us to express system-wide effects—such as expected termination intensity or the average rate of successful fork—in a way that naturally reflects the underlying topology. Note that the stationary distribution π exists for any finite, connected, undirected graph. In general, the simple RW may be periodic and alternates between partitions in the graph, but both the time-averaged and block-averaged visit frequencies equal π . The same distribution also holds exactly for the *lazy* version $\mathbf{P} = (\epsilon \mathbf{I} + (1 - \epsilon) \mathbf{P}')$, $0 < \epsilon$, which is aperiodic by construction. Therefore, in analyses that operate on time scales exceeding the mixing time T_{mix} , we can treat token locations as approximately independent draws from π .

V. EFFECTIVE TRIGGERING AGE

We start by analyzing the global fork intensity under the weak average crossing (W-AC) rule. A visit to u at time t results in a fork with probability

$$p_{\text{fork}}(u | A_u(t)) = q_u^{\text{fork}} \mathbf{1}\{A_u(t) \geq A_u\} \Pr\{T_u^+ \geq A_u\},$$

where T_u^+ is the return time of a token to node u defined as the number of time steps spent by that token to return to node u . This parametrization allows us to express the global fork intensity in terms of the return-time tail $\Pr\{T_u^+ \geq A\}$ as shown in the following lemma.

Lemma 2 (Exponential envelopes and Laplace envelopes). On a finite, lazy, irreducible, reversible Markov chain, for each node u there exist constants $c_-(u), c_+(u) > 0$ such that for all integers $A \geq 1$,

$$e^{-c_+(u) A} \pi(u) \leq \mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\} \leq e^{-c_-(u) A} \pi(u).$$

Define, for $A \geq 0$,

$$L_\pi^\pm(A) := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) e^{-c_\pm(u) A} \pi(u).$$

Then, $L_\pi^\pm(A)$ is continuous and strictly decreasing in A , with $L_\pi^\pm(0) = 1$ and $\lim_{A \rightarrow \infty} L_\pi^\pm(A) = 0$.

We define the global mean fork-per-visit intensity over all nodes as

$$p_{\text{fork}} := \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{F}_t], \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{F}_t = 1$ if the visit at time t triggers a fork and 0 otherwise. After mixing (so that visit locations are distributed according to π up to a negligible error) and assuming a uniform policy $A = A_u$, $q = q_u^{\text{fork}}$, $\forall u \in \mathcal{V}$, we define the idealized global mean fork intensity

$$p'_{\text{fork}}(A) := q \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) \Pr\{T_u^+ \geq A\}, \quad (4)$$

and we can write $p_{\text{fork}} \simeq p'_{\text{fork}}(A)$. Intuitively, W-AC activates only when the observed return-time age exceeds A , and its strength scales with the scarcity at node u through

$\Pr\{T_u^+ \geq A\}$. Combining Eq. (4) and Lemma 2, we obtain the envelope conditions

$$qL_\pi^+(A) \leq p'_{\text{fork}}(A) \leq qL_\pi^-(A). \quad (5)$$

The *effective triggering age* A_{eff} associated with an age-based policy is defined as any value $A_{\text{eff}} \geq 0$ satisfying the envelope-matching condition (Eq. (5)) after exceeding the mixing time T_{mix} . If the inequalities define an interval, we may choose any A_{eff} in that interval; all such choices lead to equivalent drift-level conclusions.

Here, p_{fork} denotes the long-run per-visit fork probability induced by the policy, which may in general involve non-uniform triggering across nodes (cf. Eq. (3)).

Thus, A_{eff} acts as a single scalar summary of the policy: it is the age at which the stationary fork intensity produced by the policy matches the graph-induced Laplace envelopes, and it fully captures the impact of the policy on the block-level drift and stability properties of the population process. For uniform policies where $A = A_u$ and $q = q_u$ for all $u \in \mathcal{V}$, we have $A_{\text{eff}} = A$. Note that A_{eff} is *not* an additional design parameter; it is an *identified scalar summary* of the stationary fork rate induced by the chosen (possibly non-uniform) age-based policy via the envelope-matching condition.

VI. PROOF SKETCH OF THEOREM 1

Let a *block* be a set of consecutive steps whose cardinality is termed as length and a *drift* be the expected change of the random process $\{Z_t\}$ from one time step to another. Let $\Phi_{\text{fork}}(t)$ and $\Phi_{\text{term}}(t)$ denote, respectively, the total numbers of forks and terminations performed at time t . Then, conditioned on Z_t , and for t exceeding T_{mix} , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[Z_{t+1} \mid Z_t] &= Z_t(1 - \Lambda_{\text{del}}) + \mathbb{E}[\Phi_{\text{fork}}(t) \mid Z_t] \\ &\quad - \mathbb{E}[\Phi_{\text{term}}(t) \mid Z_t]. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Under the one-action-per-visit rule, each individual visit to each node can trigger at most one action (fork or terminate, or pass) by the visited node, but different tokens at different nodes may act simultaneously in the same time step. Equivalently, each visit contributes at most one unit to $\Phi_{\text{fork}}(t) + \Phi_{\text{term}}(t)$ (and to the implicit trap-deletion count), while the aggregated counts $\Phi_{\text{fork}}(t)$ and $\Phi_{\text{term}}(t)$ can both be positive at a given t .

To prove Theorem 1, we convert the token-population evolution into a block-level drift statement whose leading term is expressed via the stationary law π and return-time tails, and then translate drift signs into (i) necessary viability/safety inequalities and (ii) a Foster–Lyapunov recurrence argument.

Proof sketch for Theorem 1. The formal proof builds on the following ideas.

Step 1: Mixing and block decomposition. Let \mathbf{P} be the lazy reversible RW on \mathcal{G} with stationary distribution π . Fix $\varepsilon \in (0, 1/8]$ and let $T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon)$ be the total-variation mixing time. Choose a block of length

$$B := T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon) + \kappa A_{\text{eff}}, \quad \kappa \geq 4,$$

and divide the time spent into equal-sized blocks with length B . During block k , define the block-skeleton $Z_k := Z_{kB}$. After the initial T_{mix} steps of each block, token locations are within ε of π in total variation, uniformly over starting nodes. Hence, within each block, visit locations can be coupled to i.i.d. samples from π with an $O(zB\varepsilon)$ discrepancy when conditioning on $Z_k = z$.

Step 2: Return-time tail envelopes and fork envelopes. Here we use Lemma 2 to derive the envelope-matching conditions and define A_{eff} .

Step 3: Block-level drift approximation. Condition on $Z_k = z$ and let $S_{\text{fork}}, S_{\text{del}}, S_{\text{term}}$ be the total numbers of forks, trap-deletions, and deliberate terminations during block k . By coupling-to-stationarity plus concentration for geometrically ergodic chains, these totals concentrate around their stationary means with deviations of order $\sqrt{zB \log z}$, and their expectations differ from the stationary i.i.d. surrogate by at most $O(z)$. Consequently, there exists $c_1 > 0$ such that

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] = zB(p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}}^{(k)}) \pm c_1 z,$$

where $\Lambda_{\text{del}} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}} \zeta(u)\pi(u)$ is the absorption pressure and $K_{\text{term}}^{(k)}$ is the mean deliberate termination rate in block k .

Step 4: Necessity of (V) and (S). If, at low populations, births cannot beat absorption (formally, $p_{\text{fork}} < \Lambda_{\text{del}}$ when $K_{\text{term}}^{(k)} \approx 0$), then the block drift is strictly negative for B large enough, and a standard comparison with a subcritical Galton–Watson process implies extinction with probability one. Thus avoiding extinction forces $p_{\text{fork}} \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}$, and using $p_{\text{fork}} \geq qL_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}})$ and choosing A_{eff} such that $p_{\text{fork}} = qL_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}})$, yields **(V)**: $qL_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}$.

Similarly, if at large populations the net surplus remains positive, i.e., $qL_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} > 0$, then the block drift is strictly positive for B large enough, and comparison with a supercritical Galton–Watson process yields explosion with positive probability. Hence avoiding explosion forces **(S)**: $qL_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} \leq 0$.

Step 5: Positive recurrence to a corridor. Assume there exist $0 < Z_{\text{low}} < Z_{\text{high}} < \infty$ such that **(V)** holds whenever $Z \leq Z_{\text{low}}$ and **(S)** holds whenever $Z \geq Z_{\text{high}}$. Then, for κ large enough, the block drift is uniformly positive below the corridor and uniformly negative above it. \square

VII. CONCLUSION

We study *decentralized self-regulating random walks* (SR-RWs), where nodes *fork*, *terminate*, or *pass* tokens based on return-time age, under a fork cap q and trap-induced deletions with absorption pressure Λ_{del} . Using graph-dependent *Laplace envelopes* $L_\pi^\pm(\cdot)$, we bound the stationary fork intensity via an effective triggering age A_{eff} . A block-drift analysis yields Theorem 1: viability $q, L_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}$ and safety $q, L_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} \leq 0$, implying corridor positive recurrence under margins. Future work includes tightening the envelopes and extending to time-varying graphs and improved controllers.

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APPENDIX A
LEMMA 1

We restate the lemma here for the reader's convenience.

Lemma 1 (Stationary distribution of an undirected RW). Let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ be a finite, connected, undirected graph. Consider either:

- (i) **Simple (non-lazy) random walk (SRW):** $\mathbf{P}_{uv} = 1/\deg(u)$ if $(u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$, and 0 otherwise; or
- (ii) **Weighted (non-lazy) random walk (reversible RW):** edges have symmetric weights $w_{uv} = w_{vu} \geq 0$, and

$$\mathbf{P}_{uv} = \frac{w_{uv}}{w_u}, \quad w_u := \sum_{v:(u,v) \in \mathcal{E}} w_{uv}.$$

Define

$$\pi(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{\deg(u)}{2|\mathcal{E}|}, & \text{for (i),} \\ \frac{w_u}{\sum_{x \in \mathcal{V}} w_x}, & \text{for (ii).} \end{cases}$$

Then, π is a stationary distribution: $\pi^\top \mathbf{P} = \pi^\top$ and $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) = 1$. The chain is irreducible (every node is reachable from every other). If, in addition, it is made *lazy* via $\mathbf{P}' = (\epsilon \mathbf{I} + (1 - \epsilon) \mathbf{P})$, $\epsilon > 0$, it becomes aperiodic while preserving the same stationary distribution. Consequently, for any initial distribution α ,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \alpha^\top (\mathbf{P}')^t = \pi^\top.$$

Moreover, if Z_t independent tokens evolve according to \mathbf{P} in stationarity, the random vector of node occupancies follows $\text{Multinomial}(Z_t, \pi)$.⁴

Proof. We verify reversibility with respect to π , i.e.

$$\pi(u) \mathbf{P}_{uv} = \pi(v) \mathbf{P}_{vu} \quad \forall u, v \in \mathcal{V}. \quad (7)$$

For the SRW, if $(u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(u) \mathbf{P}_{uv} &= \frac{\deg(u)}{2|\mathcal{E}|} \cdot \frac{1}{\deg(u)} = \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{E}|} \\ &= \frac{\deg(v)}{2|\mathcal{E}|} \cdot \frac{1}{\deg(v)} = \pi(v) \mathbf{P}_{vu}. \end{aligned}$$

and if $(u, v) \notin \mathcal{E}$ both sides vanish. For the weighted case, symmetry $w_{uv} = w_{vu}$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(u) \mathbf{P}_{uv} &= \frac{w_u}{\sum_x w_x} \cdot \frac{w_{uv}}{w_u} = \frac{w_{uv}}{\sum_x w_x} \\ &= \frac{w_v}{\sum_x w_x} \cdot \frac{w_{vu}}{w_v} = \pi(v) \mathbf{P}_{vu}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence (7) holds in both cases, establishing reversibility.

⁴The notation $\text{Multinomial}(Z_t, \pi)$ denotes the multinomial distribution over the n nodes, parameterized by the total number of tokens Z_t and probability vector $\pi = (\pi(u))_{u \in \mathcal{V}}$. If $N_u(t)$ is the number of tokens located at node u at time t , then $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} N_u(t) = Z_t$ and $\Pr\{N_1 = k_1, \dots, N_n = k_n\} = \frac{Z_t!}{\prod_{u \in \mathcal{V}} k_u!} \prod_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u)^{k_u}$ for $k_u \geq 0$ and $\sum_u k_u = Z_t$. Each marginal satisfies $\mathbb{E}[N_u(t)] = Z_t \pi(u)$, giving the expected number of tokens at node u under stationarity.

Summing (7) over u for a fixed v yields

$$\sum_u \pi(u) \mathbf{P}_{uv} = \pi(v) \sum_u \mathbf{P}_{vu} = \pi(v),$$

which in vector form gives $\pi^\top \mathbf{P} = \pi^\top$. Because \mathcal{G} is connected, the chain is irreducible. If the graph is bipartite (period two), the lazy modification $\mathbf{P}' = (\epsilon \mathbf{I} + (1 - \epsilon) \mathbf{P})$, $\epsilon > 0$, removes periodicity without altering π since $\pi^\top \mathbf{P}' = (\epsilon \pi^\top + (1 - \epsilon) \pi^\top \mathbf{P}) = \pi^\top$. By the Perron–Frobenius theorem [11], an irreducible, aperiodic Markov chain has a unique stationary distribution, and $\alpha^\top (\mathbf{P}')^t \rightarrow \pi^\top$ for any initial α . Finally, if Z_t tokens evolve independently under \mathbf{P} in stationarity, each has marginal distribution π , so the joint occupancy vector over \mathcal{V} is Multinomial(Z_t, π). \square

APPENDIX B
PROOF OF THEOREM 1

We restate Theorem 1 for the reader's convenience.

Theorem 1. For any decentralized age-based policy obeying the W–AC rule that avoids extinction and explosion, the following conditions must hold:

$$(V) \quad q L_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}, \quad (8)$$

$$(S) \quad q L_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} \leq 0, \quad (9)$$

where A_{eff} is the effective triggering age, K_{term} is the mean intentional termination rate, and $q \in (0, 1]$ denotes the global per-visit fork bound, i.e.

$$q := \sup_{u \in \mathcal{V}} q_u^{\text{fork}}, \quad \text{and} \quad q_u^{\text{fork}} \leq q \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{V} \geq 0.$$

Here, $q_u^{\text{fork}}(A)$ is the probability that node u forks a visiting token when its return-time age exceeds A . Conversely, suppose there exist constants $0 < Z_{\text{low}} < Z_{\text{high}} < \infty$ such that:

- the **viability condition (V)** holds whenever the population is below the corridor, which guarantees a strictly positive net birth rate when the system is under-populated;
- the **safety condition (S)** holds whenever the population exceeds the corridor, which guarantees a strictly negative net drift (births are dominated by trap-deletions plus deliberate terminations) when the population is too large.

Then the population process $\{Z_t\}$ is *positive recurrent to the corridor* $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$. That is, the Markov chain returns to the interval $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$ infinitely often with finite mean return time, and it spends a nonzero fraction of time inside the corridor in the steady state. Equivalently, $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$ is a positive recurrent (petite) set⁵ for the chain.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let \mathbf{P} be the lazy reversible RW on $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ with stationary law π . Let Z_t be the number of live tokens at (discrete) time t . Fix a tolerance parameter

⁵A subset C of the state space is called a *petite set* if there exists a nontrivial measure ν and an integer-valued sampling distribution $a(\cdot)$ such that for all $x \in C$ and all measurable A , $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a(n) P^n(x, A) \geq \nu(A)$. Intuitively, petite sets are those from which the chain can reach all regions of the state space with uniformly positive probability under a randomized (multi-step) transition. Petite sets generalize the notion of “small sets” and are the key objects used in the Foster–Lyapunov criteria for positive recurrence [9].

$\varepsilon \in (0, 1/8]$ and let $T_{\text{mix}} = T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon)$ denote the *total-variation mixing time* of the lazy random walk. Recall that for any initial distribution α over \mathcal{V} , the total-variation distance to stationarity is

$$\|\alpha^\top(\mathbf{P})^t - \pi^\top\|_{\text{TV}} := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} |\alpha^\top(\mathbf{P})^t(u) - \pi(u)|.$$

The mixing time $T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon)$ is defined as

$$T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon) := \quad (10)$$

$$\min \left\{ t \geq 0 : \max_{\alpha} \|\alpha^\top(\mathbf{P})^t - \pi^\top\|_{\text{TV}} \leq \varepsilon \right\}. \quad (11)$$

i.e., the smallest time by which *every* initial distribution is within ε total-variation distance of the stationary distribution. Choosing $\varepsilon \leq 1/8$ guarantees that after time T_{mix} , the empirical node-occupancy distribution of tokens is uniformly close to π , and all stationary expectations (e.g., trap absorption, fork intensity, return-time envelopes) incur only $O(\varepsilon)$ additive error, which is absorbed in the block-level constants used throughout the analysis. Let X_t denote the node visited at time t ; this definition applies to any lazy Markovian random walk on \mathcal{G} , since all such chains have well-defined node trajectories $\{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ generated by their transition matrix. Thus, X_t is the generic notation for the position of a token at time t , independent of the specific random-walk variant considered. This single-token random walk is used only to define return times and stationary quantities such as T_u^+ and $A_u(t)$. In the population setting below, we write $X_t^{(i)}$ for the position of the i -th token, $i \in \{1, \dots, Z_k\}$, evolving as independent lazy random walks on \mathcal{G} , and let $A_u(t) = t - L_u(t)$ be the return-time age at node u (with $L_u(t)$ the last visit time of u before t). Let $\mathcal{F}_t \in \{0, 1\}$ be the indicator of a fork event at time t (under the given decentralized policy over all nodes). Let's recall that $p_{\text{fork}} = \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{F}_t]$ which denotes the *per-visit fork probability* in the (blockwise) stationary regime. To bound $\mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\}$ note the following Lemma:

Lemma 2 (Exponential envelopes and Laplace envelopes). On a finite, lazy, irreducible, reversible Markov chain, for each node u there exist constants $c_-(u), c_+(u) > 0$ such that for all integers $A \geq 1$,

$$e^{-c_+(u)A\pi(u)} \leq \mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\} \leq e^{-c_-(u)A\pi(u)}.$$

Define, for $A \geq 0$,

$$\mathcal{L}_\pi^\pm(A) := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) e^{-c_\pm(u)A\pi(u)}.$$

Then $\mathcal{L}_\pi^\pm(A)$ is continuous and strictly decreasing in A , with $\mathcal{L}_\pi^\pm(0) = 1$ and $\lim_{A \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{L}_\pi^\pm(A) = 0$.

Proof. Because the chain is finite, lazy, and irreducible⁶, there

⁶A Markov chain is *irreducible* if every state can be reached from every other state in a finite number of steps with positive probability. For a random walk on a connected undirected graph, this property holds automatically because any pair of nodes is connected by at least one path of edges, each with nonzero transition probability. The chain being *finite* ensures that all transition probabilities are bounded away from zero along these paths, and the *laziness* (self-loop probability > 0) prevents periodicity but does not affect irreducibility.

exist integers $t_0 \geq 1$ and a constant $\varepsilon_0 \in (0, 1)$ such that the *uniform minorization* (Doebelin) holds (see, e.g., [5, Thm. 4.9, 4.10])⁷, which means that:

$$\mathbf{P}^{t_0}(x, y) \geq \varepsilon_0 \pi(y) \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \mathcal{V}. \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{P}^{t_0}(x, y)$ denotes the t_0 -step transition probability of the Markov chain, i.e., the probability of being in state y after t_0 steps when starting from x : $\mathbf{P}^{t_0}(x, y) = \mathbb{P}\{X_{t_0} = y \mid X_0 = x\}$. It is the (x, y) -entry of the t_0 -th power of the transition matrix \mathbf{P} . Fix $u \in \mathcal{V}$. Starting from any state (in particular from u just after the departure time), the probability to *hit* u within the next t_0 steps is at least

$$\mathbb{P}\{\text{hit } u \text{ in the next } t_0 \text{ steps}\} \geq \mathbb{P}\{X_{t_0} = u\} \geq \varepsilon_0 \pi(u),$$

by (12). By the strong Markov property, partition time into disjoint blocks of length t_0 . Conditional on not having hit u so far, each block independently yields a hit with probability at least $\varepsilon_0 \pi(u)$. Therefore, for any integer $m \geq 0$,

$$\mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq (m+1)t_0\} \leq (1 - \varepsilon_0 \pi(u))^m \leq \exp(-m \varepsilon_0 \pi(u)).$$

Let $A \geq 1$ and set $m = \lfloor A/t_0 \rfloor$. Then $m \geq A/t_0 - 1$, and the bound gives

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\} &\leq \exp(-\varepsilon_0 \pi(u) \lfloor A/t_0 \rfloor) \\ &\leq \exp\left(-\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2t_0} A \pi(u)\right). \end{aligned}$$

for all $A \geq 2t_0$ (absorb the finite prefix $A < 2t_0$ into the constant). Hence the upper envelope holds with

$$c_-(u) := \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2t_0} > 0.$$

Let $\varepsilon(t) := \sup_x \|\mathbf{P}^t(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}}$. By finiteness and laziness, $\varepsilon(t)$ goes to 0 as $t \rightarrow \infty$ ⁸. For the fixed node u , choose $t_u \geq T_{\text{mix}}$ such that $\varepsilon(t_u) \leq \frac{1}{2}\pi(u)$ (possible since $\varepsilon(\cdot) \downarrow 0$ for lazy reversible chains). Then, for every $x \in \mathcal{V}$ and $s \geq 1$, the total-variation bound gives

$$|\mathbf{P}^s(x, u) - \pi(u)| \leq \varepsilon(s),$$

so that

$$\mathbf{P}^s(x, u) \leq \pi(u) + \varepsilon(s).$$

⁷The *uniform minorization* (or *Doebelin*) condition means that after some fixed number of steps t_0 , the transition probabilities of the Markov chain are uniformly bounded below by a constant multiple of the stationary distribution: $\mathbf{P}^{t_0}(x, y) \geq \varepsilon_0 \pi(y)$ for all states x, y and some $\varepsilon_0 > 0$. Intuitively, this expresses that the chain has “forgotten” its starting point after t_0 steps and assigns a non-negligible probability to every state. On finite, lazy, irreducible chains, such a condition always holds because the transition graph is strongly connected and the addition of self-loops ensures that \mathbf{P}^{t_0} becomes strictly positive for some finite t_0 (i.e., the chain is *uniformly ergodic*).

⁸Because the state space is finite and the chain is lazy and irreducible, the transition matrix \mathbf{P} is stochastic with spectral radius 1 and all other eigenvalues strictly smaller in magnitude. Laziness ensures aperiodicity (each state has a positive self-loop), and irreducibility ensures the existence and uniqueness of a stationary distribution π . By the Perron–Frobenius theorem for nonnegative matrices and the spectral decomposition of stochastic operators (see, e.g., [5, Ch. 4, Thm. 4.9]), $\mathbf{P}^t(x, \cdot) \rightarrow \pi$ for every initial state x , implying $\varepsilon(t) = \sup_x \|\mathbf{P}^t(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}} \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Hence the probability to *hit* u within the next t_u steps, starting from any state, satisfies

$$\mathbb{P}\{\tau_u \leq t_u\} \leq \sum_{s=1}^{t_u} (\pi(u) + \varepsilon(s)) = t_u \pi(u) + \sum_{s=1}^{t_u} \varepsilon(s), \quad (13)$$

where τ_u is the first hitting time of u . Define

$$\theta_u := t_u + \frac{1}{\pi(u)} \sum_{s=1}^{t_u} \varepsilon(s),$$

so that

$$\mathbb{P}\{\tau_u \leq t_u\} \leq \theta_u \pi(u).$$

Now start from u immediately after a visit, and partition time into disjoint blocks of length t_u . By the strong Markov property, conditional on having avoided u so far, each block yields a return to u with probability at most $\theta_u \pi(u)$. Therefore, for any integer $m \geq 0$,

$$\mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq mt_u\} \geq (1 - \theta_u \pi(u))^m.$$

For all m such that $\theta_u \pi(u) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, we can use $1 - x \geq e^{-2x}$ to obtain

$$\mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq mt_u\} \geq \exp(-2m\theta_u \pi(u)).$$

For a general $A \geq 1$ with $m = \lfloor A/t_u \rfloor$, this yields

$$\mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\} \geq c_0 \exp\left(-\frac{2\theta_u}{t_u} A \pi(u)\right),$$

for some $c_0 \in (0, 1]$ (absorbing the finite prefix $A < 2t_u$ into c_0). Thus the lower envelope holds with the node-dependent constant

$$c_+(u) := \frac{2\theta_u}{t_u},$$

which is finite for each u and depends only on the chain's mixing profile and $\pi(u)$.

Combining the two estimates yields, for all $A \geq 1$,

$$\exp(-c_+(u) A \pi(u)) \leq \mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\},$$

$$\mathbb{P}_u\{T_u^+ \geq A\} \leq \exp(-c_-(u) A \pi(u)).$$

with strictly positive, node-dependent constants $c_{\pm}(u)$ determined by the minorization parameters (t_0, ε_0) and by the mixing profile through t_u . \square

Averaging these tails over the stationary distribution yields the *Laplace envelopes*

$$L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A) := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) e^{-c_{\pm}(u) A \pi(u)}.$$

Each $L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A)$ is continuous and strictly decreasing, with $\lim_{A \rightarrow \infty} L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A) = 0$ and $\lim_{A \rightarrow 0^+} L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A) = 1$. with $\lim_{A \rightarrow \infty} L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A) = 0$ and $\lim_{A \rightarrow 0^+} L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A) = 1$.

Choose the block length

$$B := T_{\text{mix}} + \kappa A_{\text{eff}}, \quad \kappa \geq 4,$$

and define the block times $t_k := kB$ and $Z_k := Z_{t_k}$. Let $\Lambda_{\text{del}} := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}} \zeta(u) \pi(u)$ be the *absorption pressure*.

Throughout, we assume a *one-action-per-visit discipline*⁹: during any node visit, at most one of the two actions *fork* or *terminate* may occur (never both). Each token therefore either forks once, terminates once, or passes at that visit.

Condition on $Z_k = z$. During block k , there are zB individual token-steps in total (each token moves once per time step for B steps). After the initial T_{mix} steps of the block, the lazy random walk on the finite, connected graph has mixed: the distribution of each token's position is within ε (in total variation distance) of the stationary distribution π , uniformly over all starting nodes.

To formalize this, we couple the true sequence of token locations during the block to an *idealized sequence* of zB independent samples drawn from π . Formally, a coupling means that we construct both processes—the actual random-walk visits and the idealized i.i.d. draws—on a common probability space such that their marginal distributions are correct and the probability that they disagree on any given step is at most ε . This is guaranteed by the standard ε -coupling lemma for Markov chains (see, e.g., [5, Ch. 4, Thms. 4.9–4.10]), which follows from Doeblin's uniform minorization condition for finite lazy chains.¹⁰

Under this construction, the two systems—the true and the coupled i.i.d. one—agree on all but an $O(zB\varepsilon)$ visits in expectation. That is, among the total zB token-visits within the block, the expected number of positions where the coupled processes disagree is proportional to $zB\varepsilon$. Consequently, for any bounded within-block statistic (e.g., the total number of fork or termination events), its expectation under the true process differs from that under the stationary i.i.d. surrogate by at most an $O(zB\varepsilon)$ additive term.

If we wish to keep the remainder of order $O(z)$ (as will be used in Lemma 3), we may choose the coupling precision to scale with the block length, for instance, by running the mixing prefix until the total-variation distance drops to $\varepsilon(B) = c/B$ for some constant $c > 0$. Then $zB\varepsilon(B) = O(z)$, ensuring that the overall expectation error remains $O(z)$ while preserving the same block-level asymptotics.

This approximation allows us to treat the zB visits in each block as if they were independent stationary samples drawn from π , introducing only a controlled and negligible $O(z)$ error in expectation. The next lemma formalizes this approximation.

Lemma 3. Fix a block k with length B and condition on $Z_k = z$ alive tokens at its start. Let S_{del} and S_{fork} be, respectively, the total numbers of trap-induced deletions (Pac-Man deletions) and forks that occur inside block k . Let $\Lambda_{\text{del}} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}} \zeta(u) \pi(u)$ and let p_{fork} be the per-visit fork

⁹This restriction ensures each token contributes at most one eligible event per step (either a fork or a termination), simplifying the expected-count bounds such as $\mathbb{E}[\Phi_{\text{fork}}(t) \mid Z_t] \leq Z_t q L_{\pi}^{-}(A_{\text{eff}})$.

¹⁰Informally, the ε -coupling lemma states that for any finite, irreducible, aperiodic Markov chain with mixing time $T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon)$, one can define a joint process where a copy started from any initial node and a copy started from the stationary distribution coincide after $T_{\text{mix}}(\varepsilon)$ steps with probability at least $1 - \varepsilon$.

probability induced by the policy at its effective triggering age A_{eff} (as defined in (5)). Then there exists a constant $c_0 > 0$ (depending only on the chain's mixing profile, the policy, and A_{eff} , but *not* on z or B) such that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \mathbb{E}[S_{\text{del}} \mid Z_k = z] - zB \Lambda_{\text{del}} \right| &\leq c_0 z, \\ \left| \mathbb{E}[S_{\text{fork}} \mid Z_k = z] - zB p_{\text{fork}} \right| &\leq c_0 z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Index tokens by $i \in \{1, \dots, z\}$ and let $X_t^{(i)}$ denote the location of token i at block time $t \in \{1, \dots, B\}$ (time resets at the block start). Write expectations conditional on $Z_k = z$ simply as $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$. Define the bounded indicator

$$g_{\text{del}}(u) := \mathbb{1}\{u \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{trap}}\} \zeta(u) \in [0, 1].$$

Each time a token visits u , it contributes $g_{\text{del}}(u)$ to the *expected* deletion count (and at most 1 to the realized count). Hence

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{del}} &= \sum_{i=1}^z \sum_{t=1}^B \mathbb{1}\{\text{del at } X_t^{(i)}\}, \\ \mathbb{E}[S_{\text{del}}] &= \sum_{i=1}^z \sum_{t=1}^B \mathbb{E}[g_{\text{del}}(X_t^{(i)})]. \end{aligned}$$

If a visit were exactly stationary (i.e., $X_t^{(i)} \sim \pi$), we would have $\mathbb{E}[g_{\text{del}}(X_t^{(i)})] = \sum_u \pi(u) g_{\text{del}}(u) = \Lambda_{\text{del}}$, so the stationary benchmark equals $zB \Lambda_{\text{del}}$.

For a finite, lazy, irreducible, reversible chain there exist constants $C < \infty$ and $\rho \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$\sup_{x \in \mathcal{V}} \|P^t(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}} \leq C \rho^t \quad \text{for all } t \geq 0, \quad (14)$$

(e.g., spectral-gap/mixing-time bounds; see [5, Ch. 4]). Consequently, for any bounded $f : \mathcal{V} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ and any initial state x ,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \mathbb{E}_x[f(X_t)] - \mathbb{E}_\pi[f(X)] \right| &\leq 2 \|f\|_\infty \|P^t(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}} \\ &\leq 2C \rho^t. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Applying this with $f = g_{\text{del}}$ (note $\|g_{\text{del}}\|_\infty \leq 1$), and summing over $t = 1, \dots, B$ and tokens $i = 1, \dots, z$, we obtain

$$\left| \mathbb{E}[S_{\text{del}}] - zB \Lambda_{\text{del}} \right| \leq \sum_{i=1}^z \sum_{t=1}^B 2C \rho^t \leq z \cdot \frac{2C}{1-\rho} =: c_{0,d} z.$$

This proves the first inequality with $c_{0,d} = 2C/(1-\rho)$.

Under a one-action-per-visit policy with an age trigger, the fork decision at block time t is a bounded measurable function of the lag state $Y_t = (X_{t-A_{\text{eff}}}, \dots, X_t)$. For each visit, the fork decision is a bounded measurable function of the lag state $Y_t = (X_{t-A_{\text{eff}}}, \dots, X_t)$. Let $h : \mathcal{V}^{A_{\text{eff}}+1} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denote this per-visit fork indicator. Then the total number of forks in block k is

$$S_{\text{fork}} = \sum_{i=1}^z \sum_{t=1}^B h(Y_{i,t}),$$

and the stationary per-visit fork probability is

$$p_{\text{fork}} := \mathbb{E}_\pi[h(Y)],$$

Here $\mathbb{E}_\pi[h(Y)]$ means expectation under the stationary law of the lag chain, i.e., the distribution of $(X_{t-A_{\text{eff}}}, \dots, X_t)$ when $X_t \sim \pi$.

Since $\|h\|_\infty = 1$, the standard total-variation mixing bound for lazy reversible chains ensures that there exist constants $C', \rho' \in (0, \infty) \times (0, 1)$ (depending only on (\mathbf{P}, π) and on A_{eff}) such that

$$\sup_y \|\mathcal{L}(Y_t \mid Y_0 = y) - \mathcal{L}_\pi(Y)\|_{\text{TV}} \leq C'(\rho')^t, \quad t \geq 0.$$

Here $\mathcal{L}_\pi(Y)$ denotes the stationary law of the lag chain, i.e., the distribution of $(X_{t-A_{\text{eff}}}, \dots, X_t)$ when X_t itself is distributed as π . Therefore,

$$\left| \mathbb{E}[h(Y_t)] - \mathbb{E}_\pi[h(Y)] \right| \leq 2 \|h\|_\infty C'(\rho')^t \leq 2C'(\rho')^t.$$

Summing this deviation over all zB visits in the block yields

$$\left| \mathbb{E}[S_{\text{fork}}] - zB p_{\text{fork}} \right| \leq z \sum_{t=1}^B 2C'(\rho')^t \leq z \cdot \frac{2C'}{1-\rho'} =: c_{0,f} z,$$

where

$$p_{\text{fork}} = \mathbb{E}_\pi[h(Y)]$$

is exactly the stationary per-visit fork probability defined in 3. Let $c_0 := c_{0,d} + c_{0,f}$. Then both stated bounds hold. Note that c_0 depends only on the chain's geometric mixing parameters (and on A_{eff} through the lag chain) but is independent of z and B . \square

By the W-AC (Weak Average-Crossing) triggering rule described earlier, each node u forks an arriving token with probability $q_u(A_u(t)) = q \Pr\{T_u^+ \geq A_{\text{eff}}\}$, where T_u^+ is the random return time of node u and A_{eff} denotes the *effective triggering age* at which forks are typically activated under the policy. The constant $q \in (0, 1]$ is the global upper bound on local fork probabilities, defined as

$$q = \sup_{u \in \mathcal{V}, A \geq 0} q_u(A),$$

so that no node can fork with probability exceeding q at any age. Because T_u^+ exhibits exponentially decaying tails whose rate scales with $\pi(u)$ on finite lazy reversible chains, as established by the envelope bounds

$$e^{-c_+(u)A\pi(u)} \leq \mathbb{P}\{T_u^+ \geq A\} \leq e^{-c_-(u)A\pi(u)}, \quad u \in \mathcal{V},$$

the per-visit fork probability at node u satisfies

$$q e^{-c_+(u)A_{\text{eff}}\pi(u)} \leq \mathbb{E}[\text{fork at node } u] \leq q e^{-c_-(u)A_{\text{eff}}\pi(u)}.$$

Averaging over all nodes according to the stationary distribution π gives the total mean fork probability

$$p_{\text{fork}} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) \mathbb{E}[\text{fork at node } u].$$

Substituting the above exponential envelopes yields the *graph-induced fork bounds* (or *envelopes*) that any decentralized age-based policy must satisfy, regardless of its internal randomization:

$$q L_\pi^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \leq p_{\text{fork}} \leq q L_\pi^-(A_{\text{eff}}), \quad (16)$$

where the Laplace-type functionals

$$L_{\pi}^{\pm}(A) := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) e^{-c_{\pm}(u)A} \pi(u)$$

encode how the graph topology (through π) and return-time heterogeneity (through $c_{\pm}(u)$) shape the attainable fork rates under any decentralized policy. These envelopes constitute the fundamental *graph-induced limits* that govern all subsequent viability, safety, and cost results; throughout we interpret p_{fork} as the per-visit fork probability in the block-stationary surrogate.

Let S_{term} denote the total number of deliberate (policy-driven) terminations within block k , and define its normalized mean rate as

$$K_{\text{term}} := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{V}} \pi(u) \mathbb{E}[q_u^{\text{term}}(A_u)], \quad (17)$$

Conditioned on $Z_k = z$, the block contains zB token-steps. Under the coupling argument discussed earlier, after the first T_{mix} steps, the zB visit locations can be treated as approximately i.i.d. draws from the stationary distribution π . For each token-step (i, t) , let

$$F_{i,t}, D_{i,t}, K_{i,t} \in \{0, 1\}$$

be the indicators of a fork, trap-deletion, or deliberate-terminate event. These random variables are bounded and, under the block coupling, are ε -coupled to i.i.d. draws from the stationary distribution—that is, they form a geometrically-ergodic Markov sequence whose joint law is within $O(\varepsilon)$ total variation of independence. Hence standard concentration for geometrically ergodic chains applies (see, e.g., [12, Thm. 3.16]; see also [13], [14]). Their expectations are

$$\mathbb{E}[F_{i,t}] = p_{\text{fork}}, \quad \mathbb{E}[D_{i,t}] = \Lambda_{\text{del}}, \quad \mathbb{E}[K_{i,t}] = K_{\text{term}}^{(k)}.$$

Define the corresponding blockwise totals

$$S_{\text{fork}} = \sum_{i,t} F_{i,t}, \quad S_{\text{del}} = \sum_{i,t} D_{i,t}, \quad S_{\text{term}} = \sum_{i,t} K_{i,t}.$$

Each sum involves $m = zB$ bounded terms. For any such collection of bounded or weakly dependent random variables obeying an ε -coupling to i.i.d. stationary samples, a Bernstein-type concentration inequality holds (see, e.g., [14, Thm. 2.7] for the i.i.d. case; see also [12, Thm. 3.16] and [13] for Bernstein-type concentration in geometrically ergodic Markov chains, and the spectral-gap formulation in [5, Thm. 4.6]): there exist absolute constants $C, c > 0$ such that for any $\delta > 0$,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left|\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m X_j - \mathbb{E}[X_j]\right| \geq \delta\right) \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{cm\delta^2}{1+\delta}\right) + O(m\varepsilon),$$

where ε is the coupling error from the mixing step. Choose $\delta = C\sqrt{\frac{\log z}{m}}$ with $m = zB$ (for $z \geq 2$). Then

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left|\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m X_j - \mathbb{E}[X_j]\right| \geq C\sqrt{\frac{\log z}{m}}\right) \leq 2e^{-c \log z} = 2z^{-c}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left|\sum_{j=1}^m X_j - m\mathbb{E}[X_j]\right| \geq C\sqrt{m \log z}\right) \leq 2z^{-c}.$$

for each of the sums $S_{\text{fork}}, S_{\text{del}}, S_{\text{term}}$ (after adjusting constants).

Hence, with probability at least $1 - 4z^{-c}$,

$$\left|S_{\text{fork}} - zBp_{\text{fork}}\right| \vee \quad (18)$$

$$\left|S_{\text{del}} - zB\Lambda_{\text{del}}\right| \vee \quad (19)$$

$$\left|S_{\text{term}} - zBK_{\text{term}}^{(k)}\right| \leq C\sqrt{zB \log z}. \quad (20)$$

Since the total population evolves as

$$Z_{k+1} = Z_k + S_{\text{fork}} - S_{\text{del}} - S_{\text{term}},$$

taking expectations in (18) yields

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] = zB(p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} \quad (21)$$

$$- K_{\text{term}}^{(k)}) \pm c_1 z. \quad (22)$$

where c_1 absorbs both the $O(z)$ coupling error (from approximating the true chain by stationary i.i.d. draws) and the normalized high-probability deviation $\sqrt{zB \log(z)}$ deviation (and the expectation of the deviation is $O(z)$ by integrating the tail). Here the conditional expectation is taken over all events within block k , given the starting population $Z_k = z$. The term p_{fork} denotes the mean per-visit fork probability under the blockwise stationary regime (i.e., the expected fork rate per token per step), Λ_{del} the mean per-step trap-deletion rate, and $K_{\text{term}}^{(k)}$ the deliberate-termination rate averaged over the block. Hence the drift on the right-hand side represents the expected net growth over one block of B steps, up to a controlled $O(z)$ correction arising from the mixing and coupling approximations. Choosing the block length $B = T_{\text{mix}} + \kappa A_{\text{eff}}$ with sufficiently large κ ensures that $c_1/B \leq A_{\text{eff}}^{-1/2}$, so the residual drift per step becomes asymptotically negligible. Equation (21) thus expresses the block-level population drift as a sum of mean contributions from fork, trap deletions, and deliberate terminations, up to vanishing higher-order errors.

(V) *Viability (extinction is unavoidable unless births beat absorption)*: Fix $\eta \in (0, 1)$. Assume first the strong subcritical margin

$$qL_{\pi}^{-}(A_{\text{eff}}) \leq \Lambda_{\text{del}} - 2\eta. \quad (23)$$

By the fork envelope (16), $p_{\text{fork}} \leq qL_{\pi}^{-}(A_{\text{eff}})$, hence

$$p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} \leq -2\eta.$$

Since $K_{\text{term}}^{(k)} \geq 0$, from the block-drift relation (21) we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] \leq zB(-2\eta) + c_1 z = z(-2\eta B + c_1).$$

Choose the block length $B = T_{\text{mix}} + \kappa A_{\text{eff}}$ with κ large enough so that $c_1/B \leq \eta$. Then, for all $z \geq 1$,

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} \mid Z_k = z] \leq z(1 - \eta),$$

i.e., the block-skeleton $\{Z_k\}$ has strictly negative drift. By a standard branching-process comparison,¹¹ the process $\{Z_k\}$ is stochastically dominated by a subcritical Galton–Watson process with mean offspring at most $1 - \eta$, hence $Z_k \rightarrow 0$ almost surely. Therefore, under (23), extinction occurs a.s.

Now, to obtain a *policy-agnostic necessary condition* for avoiding extinction, observe that any policy that *does not* go extinct must have nonnegative drift when the population is scarce (otherwise the process would keep drifting downward and hit zero). At scarcity, deliberate terminations vanish ($K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)} \approx 0$), so necessarily

$$p_{\text{fork}} \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}.$$

If we *parametrize* A_{eff} via the lower envelope (as allowed in the definition), namely by the identity $q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}) = p_{\text{fork}}$, then the previous inequality rewrites as

$$q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}},$$

which is exactly condition (V). (Equivalently, since $q L_{\pi}^+(A)$ is continuous and strictly decreasing in A , the inequality $p_{\text{fork}} \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}$ implies $A_{\text{eff}} \leq (L_{\pi}^+)^{-1}(\Lambda_{\text{del}}/q)$, i.e., $q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}}$.)

(S) *Safety (explosion is unavoidable unless terminations cover surplus births)*: Fix $\eta \in (0, 1)$ and suppose that there exists a positive surplus margin at large populations:

$$q L_{\pi}^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{terminate}}^{(\infty)} \geq 2\eta, \quad (24)$$

where $K_{\text{terminate}}^{(\infty)} := \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)}$ is the mean deliberate termination rate enforced by the policy at large Z . By (16), $p_{\text{fork}} \geq q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}})$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)} &\geq q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)} \\ &\geq 2\eta - (K_{\text{terminate}}^{(\infty)} - K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)}). \end{aligned}$$

For all sufficiently large k we have $K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)} \geq K_{\text{terminate}}^{(\infty)} - \eta$, and therefore

$$p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{terminate}}^{(k)} \geq \eta.$$

Plugging into (21) and choosing κ large enough so that $c_1/B \leq \eta/2$ yields, for all large z ,

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] \geq zB\eta - c_1z \geq z \frac{\eta B}{2}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} \mid Z_k = z] \geq z(1 + \eta/2),$$

¹¹One can couple $\{Z_k\}$ with a Galton–Watson (GW) process $\{\tilde{Z}_k\}$ in which each of the Z_k individuals produces an independent number of “offspring” over one block of length B , distributed as $\text{Binomial}(B, p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}}^{(k)})$. In this coupling we have $Z_k \leq_{\text{st}} \tilde{Z}_k$ for all k , and the mean offspring satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}[\tilde{Z}_{k+1}/\tilde{Z}_k] = 1 + B(p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}}^{(k)}) \leq 1 - \eta.$$

Thus the GW process is subcritical and becomes extinct almost surely, which forces $Z_k \rightarrow 0$ as well; see, e.g., [15], [16].

so the block-skeleton $\{Z_k\}$ has strictly positive drift. By the same branching-process comparison, but now from below,¹² $\{Z_k\}$ stochastically dominates a supercritical Galton–Watson process with mean offspring at least $1 + \eta/2$, and thus $\mathbb{P}(\sup_k Z_k = \infty) > 0$ (explosion with positive probability). This contradicts the assumed *avoidance of explosion*. Therefore any policy that avoids explosion must necessarily satisfy

$$q L_{\pi}^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{terminate}} \leq 0,$$

where $K_{\text{terminate}}$ denotes the mean deliberate termination rate at large Z . This is condition (S). Assume there exist $0 < Z_{\text{low}} < Z_{\text{high}} < \infty$ such that

$$(V) \quad q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}} \quad \text{whenever } Z \leq Z_{\text{low}},$$

$$(S) \quad q L_{\pi}^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} \leq 0 \\ \text{whenever } Z \geq Z_{\text{high}}.$$

Recall the block process $Z_k := Z_{t_k}$ with block length $B = T_{\text{mix}} + \kappa A_{\text{eff}}$. By block coupling to stationarity and the one-birth-per-visit discipline, there exists $c_1 > 0$ (from $O(1)$ approximation and Bernstein concentration) such that for all $z \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] \in \left[zB(p_{\text{fork}} - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}}) \pm c_1z \right], \quad (25)$$

$$p_{\text{fork}} \in [q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}), q L_{\pi}^-(A_{\text{eff}})]. \quad (26)$$

Choosing κ large (so B dominates the $O(1)$ remainder) yields margins $\eta_{\text{in}}, \eta_{\text{out}} > 0$ with:

$$\text{for } z \leq Z_{\text{low}} : \quad (27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p_{\text{fork}} &\geq q L_{\pi}^+(A_{\text{eff}}) \geq \Lambda_{\text{del}} \\ \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] &\geq \eta_{\text{in}} z, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

$$\text{for } z \geq Z_{\text{high}} : \quad (29)$$

$$p_{\text{fork}} \leq q L_{\pi}^-(A_{\text{eff}}), \quad (30)$$

$$\begin{aligned} q L_{\pi}^-(A_{\text{eff}}) - \Lambda_{\text{del}} - K_{\text{term}} &\leq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] &\leq -\eta_{\text{out}} z. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Define the Lyapunov function (distance to the corridor)

$$\begin{aligned} V(z) &:= (z - Z_{\text{low}})_+ + (Z_{\text{high}} - z)_+ \\ &= \begin{cases} Z_{\text{low}} - z, & z < Z_{\text{low}}, \\ 0, & Z_{\text{low}} \leq z \leq Z_{\text{high}}, \\ z - Z_{\text{high}}, & z > Z_{\text{high}}. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Note $V \geq 0$, piecewise linear, and $V(z) = 0$ exactly on $\mathcal{C} := \{z : Z_{\text{low}} \leq z \leq Z_{\text{high}}\}$.

For $z < Z_{\text{low}}$, (28) implies

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[V(Z_{k+1}) - V(Z_k) \mid Z_k = z] &= -\mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] \\ &\leq -\eta_{\text{in}} z \leq -\delta, \end{aligned}$$

¹²Here we couple $\{Z_k\}$ to a GW process $\{\tilde{Z}_k\}$ with mean offspring $1 + \eta/2$ such that $Z_k \geq_{\text{st}} \tilde{Z}_k$ for all large k . The GW process is supercritical and explodes with positive probability, implying $\mathbb{P}(\sup_k Z_k = \infty) > 0$; see, e.g., [15], [16].

and for $z > Z_{\text{high}}$, (31) implies

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[V(Z_{k+1}) - V(Z_k) \mid Z_k = z] &= \mathbb{E}[Z_{k+1} - Z_k \mid Z_k = z] \\ &\leq -\eta_{\text{out}} z \leq -\delta,\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\delta := \min\{\eta_{\text{in}} Z_{\text{low}}, \eta_{\text{out}} Z_{\text{high}}\} > 0.$$

Thus,

$$\mathbb{E}[V(Z_{k+1}) - V(Z_k) \mid Z_k = z] \leq -\delta, \quad z \notin \mathcal{C}. \quad (32)$$

Because the underlying walk is finite, lazy, and mixes in T_{mix} steps, the block kernel of $\{Z_k\}$ satisfies a uniform finite-step minorization on every bounded population set (Doebelin condition): for all $z \leq Z_{\text{high}}$, there exist an integer $m \geq 1$, a constant $\epsilon > 0$, and a nontrivial measure ν such that

$$\mathbf{P}^m(z, \cdot) \geq \epsilon \nu(\cdot).$$

This follows from the one-birth-per-visit discipline and the finiteness of B , which ensure that the probability of every feasible block trajectory is bounded below uniformly on compact subsets of \mathbb{N} . Hence $\mathcal{C} = \{z : Z_{\text{low}} \leq z \leq Z_{\text{high}}\}$ is a *petite set* in the sense of Meyn–Tweedie (see [9, Thm. 5.2.2]), and consequently a small set for the block chain. Together with (32), this yields positive recurrence by the drift criterion of [9, Thm. 13.0.1]. Moreover,

$$\sup_{z \in \mathcal{C}} \mathbb{E}[V(Z_{k+1}) \mid Z_k = z] < \infty,$$

since per-block increments have finite moments and z is bounded on \mathcal{C} .

The drift inequality (32) and petite set \mathcal{C} imply that the block chain $\{Z_k\}$ is positive recurrent and returns to \mathcal{C} with finite mean time (see, e.g., [9, Thm. 13.0.1]).

Because $t_{k+1} - t_k = B < \infty$, positive recurrence of $\{Z_k\}$ to \mathcal{C} transfers to positive recurrence of $\{Z_t\}$ to the corridor $[Z_{\text{low}}, Z_{\text{high}}]$. Hence, if (V) holds below and (S) holds above, the population process Z_t is positive recurrent to the corridor. \square